

THE BENEFITS OF USING INQUIRY METHOD IN TEACHING

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Abstract: In this article discusses about inquiry-based learning, kinds of inquiry method, their use by the teachers in the classroom, and their benefits in the processes of teaching and learning.

Keywords: inquiry-based learning, teaching, learning, methods, teachers, students.

Inquiry-based learning is a teaching method that encourage student to ask questions and investigate real-world problems. This type of learning has many benefits and can be used in a variety of subject area.

Inquiry-based learning is a student-centered teaching method that encourages students to ask question add investigate real-world problems. In this type of learning environment, students are actively engaged in the learning process and are given the opportunity to explore their natural curiosities.

This type of learning is often hands-on and allows students to connect what they are learning in the classroom and the real world. Inquiry-based learning has been shown to improve critical thinking skills, problem-solving skills, and creativity. [1]

The inquiry method is a student-centered learning approach with the concept of students who are activity involved in the teaching and learning activity under the monitoring and supervision of teachers. [2]

What are the types of inquiry-based learning?

Confirmation Inquiry

In this learning approach, students are posed with a question, its answer, and the method for finding the answer. They use their critical thinking and investigation skills in learning how the method works.

Open Inquiry

An open inquiry method allows students to pose original questions and investigate through their methods, presenting their results to expand their knowledge base through discussion.

Structured Inquiry

The structured Inquiry approach gives students an open question and investigation method. Then, they use this method to create an evidence-backed conclusion.

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Guided Inquiry

The guided inquiry-based learning lets students gather in groups to design investigation methods and reinforce problem-solving skills to conclude an open question. [3]

What are the benefits of Inquiry-based learning?

Four powerful benefits of inquiry-based learning

1) Increased engagement

When students are given ownership of their ideas and receive regular support and encouragement from their teachers, the benefits are astounding. One of those ways is an increased level of engagement. For example, this may look like:

- Attentive listening
- Asking deep, thoughtful questions
- Improved organization skills to make the most of their time
- Frequently in a state of “flow” (more about the concept of flow here)

Furthermore, [research has shown](#) that students who use inquiry-based approaches in the classroom are more engaged and motivated to learn. It is no wonder that when a student feels in control of their own learning, amazing things can result.

2) Stronger connections

The beauty of inquiry-based learning is that it is not confined to a single subject. In fact, you can touch on several subjects in a single session. With a focus on “big ideas”, students’ questions lead to knowledge acquisition in several subject areas. Teachers and educators need to have deep knowledge and understanding of “big ideas” that not only the curriculum demands but also the students demand. When students go through the inquiry process they discover connections between subjects they hadn’t imagined existed. For example, how mathematical concepts such as shape and line can be integrated into a beautiful painting to make it eye-catching and interesting. How can you tease out these observations?

3) Building curiosity

Curiosity is natural. From birth humans have a natural inkling towards curiosity and behave in ways that demonstrate a desire to learn about the world

around them. Even as babies, children use their senses to explore their new world. As they get older, they build upon this foundation of curiosity. Furthermore, they replace simple observation with asking questions about the things they see, feel, touch, and hear around them. Their natural curiosity is nurtured, and their spark of wonder and learning becomes alive and nourished.

4) Skill development

The most important skills in the 21st century are no longer fact memorization or rote learning. Instead, an understanding of acquiring and making sense of the mass amounts of data available to our students is key. During inquiry-based learning, teachers and educators need to go beyond information accumulation and focus more on seeking appropriate resolutions to questions and issues that are important for their students and the world around them. Consequently, nurturing the development of inquiry skills, as well as the attitudes or habits that will help students make sense of their learning, is crucial. Some of these skills include:

- Critical thinking during reading and listening
- Skimming and scanning techniques
- Note taking (jot notes, sketching, etc)
- Deciphering what information is useful and what is not
- Self-assessment and reflection
- Responsibility, organization, independent work
- Collaboration and teamwork [4]

One of the most useful methods which is used in all educational activities and in teaching process is the question and answer (inquiry) method. The question and answer method is used to motivate, stimulate curiosity, strengthen thinking and activate students. The main benefits of using inquiry method is arouse students' curiosity and encourage them to think and understand new things. Students think through questions ana analysis different parts of a subject. They compare its different parts and can understand the value of the topics.

References:

1. What Is Inquiry-Based Learning? Types, Benefits, Examples [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://www.splasglearn.com/blog/what-is-inquiry-based-learning-a-complete-overview/>
2. ERIC – EJ1256067 – Inquiry Method in the Teaching and Learning Process, Shanlax International of Education, 2020-Jun [Electronic resource]. Access mode:

<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1256067#:~:text=The%20inquiry%20method%20is%20a,inquiry%20method%20in%20the%20classroom.>

3. Benefits of Inquiry-based Learning And Noisy Classroom [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://www.edteacherview.in/trends-insight/benefits-inquiry-based-learning-noisy-classrooms/>

4. Powerful Benefits of Inquiry-Based Learning by Inquiry [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://www.learningbyinquiry.com/4-benefits-of-inquiry-based-learning/>

5. The system of exercises in teaching foreign language in school and universities. Interuniversity collection of scientific papers, ed. Shatilova S.F.L. – 1778.- P.55.

6. Edge, J. (1993) Essentials of English Language Teaching. Addison Wesley.

